

DEVELOPMENT AND ITS EFFECTIVENESS OF SELF-AWARENESS AND INTERPERSONAL RELATION SKILLS EDUCATION PROGRAM FOR STUDENT TEACHERS

Dr. Usha P. More

Assistant Professor,

SNDT College of Education, Pune.

Abstract:

National Curriculum Framework 2005 mention the while discussing of objectives of Education should develop in a person ability of thinking and making Ethical decision independently or in a group. It is essential to sensitize students regarding emotions and well beings of others and develop commitment for values based on knowledge and understanding of Worlds. If teachers understand their students in social, cultural and political context then only they can mould their students having in mind-economical social, political and cultural objectives of national development. To understand others, co. Operations, social responsibility and good Interpersonal relations both of teacher and students. Need of self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills Education in school environment.

Kay words: *Would be teacher, self-awareness skill, Interpersonal skills, Effectiveness*

Introduction:

Education is always considered as a Powerful tool for the development of an individual and society. Education being subsystem of a society is the process of achievement of a better quality of life. Education in 21st century is expected to contribute for generation of information, its storage and its dissemination. Each individual must be aware of and must be ready for taking benefits of future opportunities using his knowledge, skills and attitude and also adjusting himself to various situations. Considering this, UNESCO'S Report highlights four pillars of education as the main purpose of education (UNESCO 1996)

1) **Learning to know** –Acquiring tools of acquisition of knowledge.

- 2) **Learning to do** – Developing skill for application of acquired knowledge and dealing creatively with one’s environment.
- 3) **Learning to live together** – Participating and co-operating with others in all human activities.
- 4) **Learning to be** – Developing oneself to achieve above three.

These Four pillars are interlinked and interdependent. They also reflect self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills. Self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills are Life skills .It is very essential to make efforts for the acquisition of life skills through education.

Need of self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills in School Education:

This era is of competitions, conflict and hectic schedule. Materialism is decaying and affecting ethics. Every individual in this society has to face conflict, competition, and stress in every walk of life. Nuclear Families have over expectation from their kids. There is undue comparison with other students due to lack of art of parenting. All this affects the child’s mind. It is resulting into number of problems such as fear of failure, suicides, aggressiveness, inferiority or superiority complexes, loneliness, criminal attitude anxieties etc. Many times, students become victims of ragging in colleges. To avoid consequences of factors it is important to impart of Self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills in school education. Every individual wants to be happy, satisfied, and successful, in his/her life

Hence self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills. Education’ should be a part of school education.

- Self-awareness skill
- Interpersonal Relation Skill

Benefits of the use of self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills:

1. Complete Personality Development: -

They are helpful to live a positive life and achieve individual development. Development of self-awareness, self-pride and confidence help the person understand his limitations. A person becomes ready to identify and understand the opportunities and face threat in life through development of self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills.

2. Development of community through Interpersonal skills:-

Self-Awareness skills and Interpersonal relation skills help the students to understand development of family and society. Interpersonal skills are useful to solve positively the problems in their personal and public life.

Social Development:

While solving social problems, a person having knowledge of Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal relation skills can think of alternative methods and their pros and cons. Positive interpersonal relations promote social development. Interpersonal skills improve relationships among persons resulting into effective team activities and projects. These skills are especially useful to teachers in educational transactions.

Development of Environmental Skills:

Globalization has brought new life style and technology leading to destruction of environment. Students must be aware of protection of environment. Self-Awareness and Interpersonal relation skills was sensitize students about the environment issues for human existence and sustainable development.

Importance of Self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills in Teacher Education:

It is important to produce capable teachers who can understand problems and needs of students and respond accordingly. Teachers themselves must be capable to impart Self-awareness skill and Interpersonal skills among students. Once teachers acquire this Self-awareness skill and Interpersonal skills they can apply them in their personal life as well as in improvisation of teaching. Hence pre service teacher education should plan to include Self-awareness skill and Interpersonal skills in the syllabus itself. This will enable the teachers to think independently, to upgrade themselves to respond according to students' needs. National Curriculum Framework 2005 also puts forth need of imparting Self-awareness skill and Interpersonal skills

Need and Importance of the Present Research:

Review of related researches reveals that there is no single research done in area of teacher education for imparting all life skills in would be teachers. Few attempts to impart single skill proved that programs were effective to develop only that skill.

In this respect it is essential to impart life skills education to would be teacher to make them able to accept such responsibility in future. Review of related researches underlined the need for development of self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills education program. There are no tools and tests available to measure these self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills. Hence there is a need to prepare such educational program for imparting these skills and study its effectiveness.

The plan of present study is developed keeping in view all these intensions.

Title of Research:

Development and its Effectiveness of self-Awareness and Interpersonal Relation Skills Education Program for Student teachers

Objectives of the study:

- 1) To prepare a Self-Awareness skills Interpersonal skills Program for would be teachers.
- 2) To study the effectiveness of the Self Awareness skills Interpersonal skills Education Program.

Operational definitions of the terms:

Would be teacher: All the students enrolled for B.Ed. course. Of S.N.D.T. college of Education Pune.

Self-Awareness: Self-awareness means to identify own emotions, capacities, limitations, and skills to evaluate one self. Self-awareness was measured in terms of score obtained on test of self-awareness developed by the researcher.

Interpersonal relations: Interpersonal relations means ability to understand, maintain and develop the relations with those concerned with day-to-day life. Interpersonal relations was measured in terms of score obtained on test of Effective Interpersonal relations developed by the researcher.

Self-awareness and Interpersonal relation Skills Education Program:

A Special program prepared by the researcher to impart Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal relation skills amongst the would be teachers.

Total duration of the program was 60 clock hours in which 30 hours was given Theoretical orientation of Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal skills given through worksheets and printed self-learning material. 30 hours are assigned to practical work. The practical will provide practice to would be teachers for applying

skills during teaching and interactions with students in school environments in simulated condition. Practical work will include role play, simulation and games, group discussions, group interaction, brain storming, sharing experiences, self-demonstrations, SWOT analysis and visits to social institutions.

The activities were used according to the nature of the skills.

Effectiveness: The positive difference in the mean scores of would be teachers on pretest and posttest about Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal relation skills developed by the researcher.

Research Hypotheses:

There will be positive and significant difference in pre-test and post-test mean scores of would-be teachers after implementation of ‘Education Program.’

Research Method: The experimental method was used suitable to objectives of the study.

Experimental Design: Single group pretest test post design was used. It is represented diagrammatically below.

Variables in the research:

Independent Variable: A Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal skills education program for the would be teachers of secondary level developed by the researcher.

Dependent Variable: An aggregate score of would be teachers on the tests of Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal skills.

Controlled Variable: The pretest and post tests on Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal skills prepared by the researcher was parallel.

Sample: Incidental sampling was used. All the students enrolled for B.Ed. course in S.N.D.T. College of Education Pune, was included.

Tools and Techniques used data for analyses:

1. 't' Test: Significance of the difference between mean scores of self-awareness and Interpersonal skill measurement in pretest and posttest was tested by using 't' test.
2. Qualitative analysis: open responses on training program test and feedback questioner were analyzed qualitatively.

Implementation of Study:

- 1) Self-Awareness skills and Interpersonal relation skills Education” program was prepared by collecting information from various sources.

- 2) Pretest prepared and administered before the implementation of the program.
- 3) **Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal relation skills Program:** A Special programme developed by the researcher to impart Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal relation skills amongst the would be teachers. Total duration of the program was of 60 clock hours in which 30 hours was assigned to Theoretical work. Theoretical orientation given through worksheets and printed self-learning material.

30 ours was assigned to practical work.

- 3) Identifying various Activities, like Practical work was include role play, simulation and games, group discussions, group interaction, brain storming, sharing experiences, self-demonstrations, SWOT analysis and visits to social institutions. According to activity the practical will be completed in whole class or in small groups partials of life skills included in syllabus will be implanted along with routine timetable. Researcher was conduct reaming practical work through extra periods.

After implementation of ‘Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal relation skills Education program parallel posttest was administered. Feedback also will be taken with the help of a questionnaire.

Pretest on Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal relation skills was developed and administered to before the implementation of the program in the beginning of the test also was given.

Qualitative analysis:

Qualitative analysis on the basis of open responses of the question in Effective communication skills test, selected activities of self-learning material in teaching program and open responses of feedback questionnaire.

In of skills pre-test and self-awareness and Interpersonal relation post-test included five open ended questions. Responses of the would-be Teachers to these questions were analyzed on the basis of frequently

Responses of the training program feedback questionnaire of the would-be Teachers on the various activities included in the training program were analyzed qualitatively.

Conclusion of the Research (Limited to the sample in experiment):

1. The post-test means score of self-awareness and interpersonal relation skills Measurement of student teachers is found significantly higher than that of pretest mean score. That means Effective communication skills education program prepared by the researcher based on self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills given by WHO was in developing self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills of B.Ed. Student Teachers.
2. Open responses of posttest are qualitatively better as compared to responses on pretest regarding fluency, flexibility, and originality. Hence the self-awareness and interpersonal relation skills Education Program implemented by the researcher has proven to be effective for developing self-awareness and Interpersonal relation skills.

The researcher proved to be effective be for developing, Empathy, Interpersonal relation and self-awareness skill

Scope and limitations of the study:

- 1) Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal relation skills included in the present study.
- 2) Duration of the 'self-Awareness skills and Interpersonal relation skills education program was of 60 clock hours in which 30 hours assigned to practical work. Theoretical orientation was given through worksheets and printed self-learning material.
- 3) Self Awareness skills and Interpersonal relation skills education program is short duration.
- 4) This program included 46 B.Ed. students of S.N.D.T. collage of Education (IASE) Pune 38
- 5) Sample included only female students.
- 6) Data collection tools are not standardized prepared by researcher.

There were limitations to broader generalizations of the conclusions due to incidental sample and tools prepared by researcher.

Bibliography:

- 1) A Report on – Life skills Education programme jointly organization by the Maharashtra Prathmik Shikshan Parishad and UNICEF Mumbai on 4-6 October,

- 2006 hosted by INSIGHT Institute for Human Growth Vadodara (Gujrat).
- 2) Singh Dalip (2001), “Emotional Intelligence”; at work, Response books, A division of sage publication India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi 110048.
 - 3) Gilhooly, K.J. (1988), “Thinking” ; second edition, Academic press Inc. san Dieya, CA 92101.
 - 4) Goleman, Danial (1995), “Emotional intelligence”; New York, Toronto London Sydney Auckland
 - 5) Goleman, Danial (2007), “Social Intelligence” ; Arrow Books London
 - 6) Krishna Mohan, Banersi, Meera (1990) “Developing Communication skills”; S.G. Wasani for Macmillan India limited New Delhi – 110002.
 - 7) Moore, Edgar, (1967), “Creative and Critical Thinking” ; Houghton miffing company boston.
 - 8) Patty, Geoffrey (1998), “How to be better at creativity”; The Industrial Society, 48 Bryanston square London.
 - 9) UNESCO, (1996), “Learning the treasure within report to UNESCO of the International Commission on Education for the Twenty First Century”; Paris UNESCO.
 - 10) Wellington C. Baelish, Wellington Jean, (1960), “Teaching for Critical Thinking”; Mc Grow Hill Book company, New York, London.

Websites:

- 1) <http://www.eric.ed.gov> /ERIC web portal as on –
- 2) <http://www.undoc.org/pat/youth net/action/message escape-peers->
- 3) <http://www.unicef.org /life skills/index which skills.html> as on 1
- 4) life skills syllabus India – yahoo